

CORROSION SCIENCE

Title: Direct sub-nanometer scale electron microscopy analysis of anion incorporation into self-ordered anodic alumina layers

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Abstract

Ordered porous alumina layers prepared by two-step anodising in phosphoric, oxalic and sulphuric acids have been characterized at sub-nanometer scale using electron microscopy techniques. FEG-SEM and STEM-HAADF images allowed estimating the pore size, cell wall and pore wall thicknesses of the layers. Nanoanalytical characterization has been performed by STEM-EELS and STEM-X-EDS. Detailed features of the spatial distribution of anions in the pore wall of the films have been obtained. Maximum concentration of P-species occurs, approximately, at the middle of the pore wall; adjacent to the pore for C-species, whereas the distribution of S-species appears to be uniform.

Keywords: A: Aluminium; B: SEM; B: STEM; C: Anodic film

1. Introduction

Anodising of aluminium alloys has been employed as surface protection treatment since the 1920s [1]. The first attempts to characterize the oxide layers formed were carried out early afterwards [1] but the first TEM images of anodic alumina layer were reported during the 1970s, working in cross-section bright field mode (BF-TEM). Those images revealed a structure composed of two clearly differentiated regions: a thick outer porous layer and a thin compact inner layer in contact with the non-oxidized aluminium substrate, the so-called barrier layer. The porous layer part is composed of an array of parallel-sided hexagonal cells, containing a pore in the centre, and showing certain short range order. Nevertheless, this array contains a high concentration of varied defects as pentagonal cells, branched pores or lack of parallelism, among others. Nowadays, these kinds of anodic alumina layers are called *disordered* layers.

Characterization studies performed between the 1970s and the early 1990s [2–9] also showed that the porous layer is in fact composed of two structurally different regions, as Fig. 1 depicts. The first region is the pore wall, which is the region closer to the pore in which anions from the electrolyte (SO_4^{2-} , PO_4^{3-} , $\text{C}_2\text{O}_4^{2-}$, etc.) are incorporated during the anodising process. The second region is

the so-called cell walls; this is the oxide area farther from the pores which outlines the boundaries with the neighbouring cells. This area is made of nearly pure alumina and, therefore, mostly free of anions of the electrolyte.

However, due to the difficulties inherent to direct measurements, indirect methods were employed in some cases to establish the occurrence of these two regions [3,7,8]. These studies were based in the analysis of the changes in morphology suffered by these two regions when exposed to the influence of the high energy (a few hundred keVs) electron beam of a transmission electron microscope. The results they obtained did in fact show that the anion-free region changed in quite a different way to that of the anion-contaminated one. With this experimental approach, it could be determined that the thickness of the anion-free region depends on the specific chemical nature of the acid employed during the anodising process.

Afterwards, direct evidences of the actual occurrence of ions coming from the electrolyte inside oxide films formed in phosphoric acid [4,6,9] were provided. By acquiring X-EDS spectra at different spots located within the anion-contaminated region, they observed that the phosphorus concentration decreased as the probe moved away from the areas close the pore edges towards

the cell walls. Although the presence of phosphorus in this region was further confirmed by Thornton and Furneaux [6], on the basis of X-EDS maps recorded on TEM samples prepared by ion-milling, no preferential concentration of this element was reported. The

Fig. 1. Scheme showing the anion-free and the anion-contaminated zones of a porous anodic alumina layer. (Adapted from [3].)

spatial resolutions achievable in analytical mode in the equipments employed in those studies were in the order of some tens of nanometers. This is why they were limited to alumina films anodised in phosphoric acid, for which the cell parameters are several tens of nanometer. Alumina films anodised in sulphuric and oxalic acid have much smaller cell walls, pore walls and pore diameters; their chemical characterization becoming totally unreliable using electron probes of about the same dimensions. Moreover, most of the revised characterization literature mentioned above was performed on ion-beam thinned samples. Considering that the structure of the films is severely affected by electron beam irradiation, it seems reasonable to think that an ion beam bombardment could also introduce structural and/or chemical modifications in an unpredictable way. If so, the characterization results could not exactly correspond to the pristine anodic films.

The whole set of papers commented on above did focus on disordered porous alumina layers. Masuda and Fukuda prepared in 1995 [10] the first anodic porous alumina films showing long-range order. This kind of anodic alumina layers are those referred as *ordered* layers. Soon after, Masuda and Satoh [11] published an improved method to obtain these ordered layers: the two-step anodising method. BF-TEM images of the ordered films obtained in phosphoric, sulphuric and oxalic acid allowed Gösele et al. [12] to report that, in contrast to disordered porous alumina layer, the anion-free and anion-contaminated regions show the same relative thickness in the case of ordered porous alumina layer, regardless of the acid employed during anodising.

Ordered porous alumina layers have extended the employment of anodising beyond its classical protective purpose. Thus, in the last years they have attracted important attention due to its pecu-

Table 1
Anodising conditions.

Electrolyte	Concentration (M)	Voltage (V)	Temperature (°C)
H ₂ SO ₄	0.3	25	2–4
C ₂ H ₂ O ₄	0.3	40	2–4
H ₃ PO ₄	0.1 ^a	195	2–4

^a To avoid breakdown, first anodisation in phosphoric acid begins with 0.05 M in weight and 3 h later concentrated H₃PO₄ is added to reach 0.1 M.

Table 2
Treatment conditions of immersion in H₃PO₄ solutions to detach the alumina membrane from the aluminium substrate after anodising and step-wise reduction potential.

Anodizing electrolyte	Detaching electrolyte (M)	Temperature (°C)	Time (min)
H ₂ SO ₄	H ₃ PO ₄ 0.5	Room	10
C ₂ H ₂ O ₄	H ₃ PO ₄ 0.5	35	10
H ₃ PO ₄	H ₃ PO ₄ 1.0	45	10

liar periodic nanostructure, being widespread employed as template for the synthesis of new nanomaterials [13–18] or explored as photonic crystal [19,20], photoluminescence material [21] or sensor [22]. Consequently, improved studies concerning mechanism of growth of alumina layer have been taken up again as key issue [23–28]. However, to our knowledge, there is only one paper devoted to direct characterization of ion incorporation into ordered

Fig. 2. FEG-SEM images of a porous alumina membrane obtained in phosphoric acid anodising. (a) Top view of hexagonal cells with pores in the centre. (b) Top view digitally analyzed to measure pore diameter (coloured regions) distribution. (c) Cross-section view showing the parallel growth of the nanopores. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Fig. 3. (a) STEM-HAADF image of an ultramicrotomed section of an ordered porous alumina membrane formed in phosphoric acid. The image shows a hexagonal cell with a pore in the centre. (b-d) X-EDS spectra acquired in the positions marked in the STEM-HAADF image.

Table 3
X-EDS analysis for Al and P in the positions marked in Fig. 3(a).

	Al (atomic %)	P (atomic %)
Position 1	99.88	0.12
Position 2	90.53	9.47
Position 3	92.27	7.73

pore alumina structure [29]. The authors only accomplish a limited X-EDS line analysis on very thick (200 nm) samples of ordered alumina layers grown in oxalic acid. In this scenario, it seems clear

that a reliable and comprehensive structural and chemical characterization study of ordered anodic alumina layers is appealing.

In this paper we have performed a detailed study, using both transmission and scanning-transmission imaging and nanoanalytical electron microscopy techniques, to characterize ordered anodic alumina layers. To avoid sample-preparation artefacts and to minimise as much as possible the size of the volume from which analytical information was generated, ultrathin (thickness less than 20 nm) samples prepared by ultramicrotomy have been used. A comparative study of layers prepared in phosphoric, sulphuric and oxalic acids is also done. As imaging techniques both HREM (High-resolution Electron Microscopy) and STEM-HAADF (Scanning-Transmission Electron Microscopy working in High Angle

Annular Dark Field) are used. To our knowledge, the latter technique has never been reported on this type of samples although it provides quite interesting images whose contrasts are related to chemical (atomic number) variations. We have performed nano-analysis using both STEM-X-EDS and Electron Energy Loss Spectroscopy (EELS). When the last analytical approach is used in STEM mode, with a very fine (0.5 nm) electron probe, a much higher spatial resolution is achievable in the experiments. This is the case required in the analysis of layers prepared both in sulphuric and oxalic acid. We have used not only the spot analysis approach but also the so-called spectrum line and spectrum imaging modes. These techniques have been used to retrieve very high spatial resolution analytical information about the chemical element distribution in these samples.

The whole set of data here presented provides a novel, updated, and comparative view about the element distribution in ordered anodic alumina layers which could eventually be of great interest to improve the current understanding of their growth mechanism.

2. Experimental

2.1. Oxide layers preparation

The starting anodising material was a high purity aluminium alloy (>99.999%) supplied by Goodfellow. Before anodising, the aluminium samples were pre-treated using two consecutive surface treatments: degreasing with acetone and further electropolishing

in a $\text{HClO}_4/\text{EtOH}$ (vol/vol = 1:3) solution at 0 °C applying 20 V during 4 min with a Grelco GVD310 power supply. Anodising was performed, using a electrochemical cells of 125 mL of capacity, under constant voltage conditions. Table 1 summarizes the experimental details employed in each anodisation treatment.

To remove the alumina layer after the first anodisation treatment, the anodised samples were immersed in H_3PO_4 0.6 M at room temperature with magnetic stirring during 20 h.

Afterwards, the second anodisation was performed in the same conditions as previously, Table 1. Only in the case of phosphoric media there is a small difference, since the treatment runs with 0.1 M concentration from the beginning.

Once the ordered porous alumina layers were obtained, they were detached from the aluminium substrate by firstly, the step-wise reduction potential method and secondly, subsequent immersing in H_3PO_4 solutions. Table 2 shows concentration and temperature of the phosphoric solution as well as immersion time used in the second part of this procedure.

2.2. Oxide layers characterization

Morphological and chemical characterization of the alumina membranes was realized by means of various electron microscopy techniques.

FEG-SEM images of the membranes were acquired in a FEI SIRION microscope. For TEM related techniques slices of the membranes of 15 nm of thickness were obtained in an ultramicro-

Fig. 4. X-EDS intensity of Al and P signals (left) obtained along the line marked in the STEM-HAADF image (right), acquired in a porous alumina membrane anodised in phosphoric acid.

Fig. 5. (a) STEM-HAADF image of a porous alumina membrane obtained in phosphoric acid anodising. Compositional maps of (b) P and (c) Al acquired in the square area marked in (a).

tome model EM UC6 from Leyca Microsystems cutting with a diamond knife. A JEOL2010F microscope, working at 200 kV, was used to characterize the samples. This instrument has a structural resolution of 0.19 nm and it is equipped with a HAADF detector, an EELS spectrometer (GIF2000 Gatan Imaging Filter) and a X-EDS, Oxford INCA Energy 2000 system. The morphological information was provided analyzing STEM-HAADF (High Angle Annular Dark Field-Scanning-Transmission Electron Microscopy) using a 0.5 nm probe size and a 12 cm camera length.

The nanoanalytical studies were performed by combining HAADF images with spectroscopy techniques as X-EDS and EELS, using a 0.5 nm probe size and a 12 cm camera length. The X-EDS spectra were performed using the spot and elemental mapping mode, whereas EELS spectra were recorded using the spectrum imaging (SI) mode. The SI mode consists on acquiring a collection of spectra at successive positions separated by a distance slightly larger than the beam size (0.8 nm in our case) while the fine electron probe (0.5 nm in our experiments) is scanned over a predefined region in the sample. The HAADF signal is also collected at each point of the scan. This approach allows correlating nanoanalytical and structural information of the region under study. The spectra, with 0.3 eV energy dispersion, were recorded using an acquisition time of 3–5 s and convergence and collection semi-angles of 8 mrad and 24 mrad, respectively.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Phosphoric acid anodising

Fig. 2 shows three FEG-SEM images of a sample anodised in phosphoric acid. It can be observed, Fig. 2(a), that the anodising procedure leads to a honeycomb-like arrangement of hexagonal cells with a pore in their centre which shows long-range order. Although the experimental conditions employed during anodising were those specifically devised to prepare ordered layers, the anodic films still contain some defects, as those observed at the right side of the image. To estimate the pore diameter of these films in a statistically meaningful way, these FEG-SEM images have been digitally processed. Thus, Fig. 2(b) is a FEG-SEM image in which pore regions analyzed appear coloured. The average pore size estimated from the pore size distribution is 180 nm. Fig. 2(c) shows a cross-section view of the membrane shown in Fig. 2(a) which confirms that the pores grew parallel to each other.

Fig. 3 shows a representative STEM-HAADF image of one ultramicrotomed section of the alumina film, Fig. 3(a), and X-EDS spectra acquired in the spots marked on the image, Fig. 3(b–d). In the STEM-HAADF included in Fig. 3(a), different neighbouring hexagonal cells can be observed. Note that three regions of different contrast can be observed in this image: (1) a bright and thin hexagonal band, which corresponds to the cell walls; (2) a darker area inside this band, which corresponds to the pore wall and (3) a black hole at the centre, the pore. These regions were described in Fig. 1. To obtain information about the element distribution in this structure, X-EDS spectra were collected at a position inside the cell wall, that marked as 1, in a region inside the pore walls, location 2, and finally at a location very close to the pore mouth, that labelled as 3. Note that P peaks are only seen in the X-EDS spectra recorded on spots outside the cell wall. To confirm this, Table 3 displays data corresponding to the semiquantitative analysis of Al and P contents in these positions. These data indicate that there is almost no detectable phosphorus in the cell wall, position 1. The second finding is that the pore wall contains phosphorus, the concentration of this element being, at the position far from the pore, higher than that observed at sites adjacent to the pore. These results are in good agreement with those reported by Thompson et al. [4].

To obtain more precise information about the spatial distribution of P and Al in these films two additional experiments were performed, X-EDS spectrum-line analysis and X-EDS element distribution mapping. Fig. 4(a) plots the evolution of the X-EDS intensity of Al and P signals along a line which crosses three cells, as marked in the STEM-HAADF in Fig. 4(b). It can be seen that the signals corresponding to these two elements follow reversed trends throughout the scanned line. Thus, P intensity comes to minimum values in the areas of the pore wall adjacent to the pore and also in the cell wall. It displays maximum values about the middle of the pore wall area. Let us highlight that the P content inside the pore wall is, Table 3, close to zero. Gösele et al. [19] suggested that a similar P distribution should exist to explain the non uniform refractive index of the pore wall of ordered alumina layers obtained in phosphoric anodising. Concerning Al distribution, the signal shows the opposite trend, with a maximum in the cell wall,

Fig. 6. Intensity profiles of STEM-HAADF signals in different areas of the images employed to measure (a) cell wall thickness, (b) pore wall thickness and (c) pore diameter.

decreases to a minimum value in the centre of the pore wall area and increasing again towards the pore edge.

Fig. 5 reports the Al and P map distributions. Note once more that the two maps are complementary to each other. Fig. 5(b) confirms that P concentrates in the pore wall area, while it is almost not detected in the cell walls. The elemental distribution map of Al indicates the presence of aluminium all over the film but its concentration is higher in the cell walls.

The STEM-HAADF images are worth of further comment in the light of this nanoanalytical information. Let us recall that contrasts in this type of image can be due to both thickness variations in samples of homogeneous composition or to variations in the average atomic number (Z) along the beam path in samples with same thickness. Therefore, thicker regions in compositionally homogeneous samples and regions with higher average atomic number in samples with the same thickness will appear as brighter regions. In the case of samples prepared by ultramicrotomy thickness can be assumed to be constant along the whole TEM specimen. So, the average Z is the key factor to interpret the contrast differences between cells and pore wall. To estimate this parameter, two factors must be considered: the chemical composition and the density of the material.

Our STEM-X-EDS results and those reported by Thompson et al. [4,5] and Ono et al. [8,9] indicate that the pore wall and the cell wall contain different concentrations of the electrolyte ion, phosphate ions presumably. Then, if contrasts in STEM-HAADF images were solely due to changes in composition, the incorporation of phosphorus into the pore wall should increase the brightness of the pore wall, since phosphorus-contaminated regions would have a higher average atomic number ($P = 15$; $Al = 13$) than anion-contamination free regions. Note that the STEM-HAADF images show exactly the opposite behaviour.

The second factor contributing to the image signal, as mentioned above, is the density of the material. A higher density means more atoms in the same volume, a higher average Z per thickness unit and, as a consequence, more intensity. After ruling out the

influence of chemical composition, we must admit that the contrasts observed in our STEM-HAADF images must be due to a higher density of the material in the cells walls. Very likely, the incorporation of Phosphorus-containing ions into the pore walls results in a decrease of the density. This change in density should be high enough to compensate the expected intensity increase due to the higher average atomic number caused by the incorporation of phosphorus-containing ions to the pore walls.

At this point, it is worthy of comment one limitation of the BF-TEM images widespread employed in the bibliography. In effect, it is important to emphasize that the contrasts observed in bright field images cannot be unambiguously attributed not neither to changes in composition nor to thickness variations, since there is also a diffraction contrast contribution in this type of imaging mode; i.e. two areas of the same thickness and composition can appear with quite different brightness in the image if there are differences in their electron diffraction behaviour. In other words, one cannot simply assume that darker regions in BF-images necessarily correspond to thicker, or denser, regions, even if they are compositionally homogeneous.

STEM-HAADF images have also allowed us to measure pore diameters, pore wall thickness and cell wall thickness using intensity profiles. Fig. 6(a) shows an HAADF-image intensity profile along a line crossing a cell wall. Note the presence of a zone of higher intensity, which corresponds to the cell wall which is about 60 nm wide in this case. This means that each cell contributes to this wall thickness with about 30 nm. This value corresponds to the average cell wall thickness obtained after measuring on a large number of cells in images like the one shown here. Likewise, it was possible to measure the pore wall thickness, Fig. 6(b), and the pore diameter, Fig. 6(c). The average values for these parameters were 122 nm and 174 nm, respectively. Note that the estimated pore size is very close to that calculated from FEG-SEM images, Fig. 2(b).

The high quality of the elemental distribution maps allows obtaining intensity profiles from these images. Fig. 7(a) shows a representative intensity profile obtained from the P map

Fig. 7. (a) Intensity profiles obtained in the same cell wall of a porous alumina membrane anodised in phosphoric acid from (b) a STEM-HAADF image and (c) the corresponding compositional map of P.

Fig. 8. FEG-SEM images of a porous alumina membrane obtained in oxalic acid anodising. (a) Top view. (b) Top view digitally analyzed to measure pore diameter (coloured regions) distribution. (c) Cross-section view showing the parallel growth of the nanopores. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

(Fig. 7(b)). For comparison, the profile of the STEM-HAADF image of the mapped area, shown in Fig. 7(c), is also included. Note that the cell wall thickness that can be estimated from the P-map intensity profile is very similar to that obtained from the STEM-HAADF image, this suggesting that the cell wall is free of phosphorus throughout its width.

As already mentioned, Gösele et al. [12] found that the D_{inner}/D_{outer} ratio in nanoporous alumina films is approximately

0.2 ± 0.02 when self-ordering regimes are employed for anodising, where D_{inner} and D_{outer} stand for the cell wall and the pore wall thickness, respectively. In the present work, according to the data we have presented the D_{inner}/D_{outer} ratio results 0.24, a little bit higher but still in very good agreement with the results reported by Gösele.

3.2. Oxalic acid anodising

Representative FEG-SEM images of a sample anodised in oxalic acid are included in Fig. 8. Analyzing the membrane in top view, the morphology looks similar to that of the membranes obtained by anodising in phosphoric acid, Fig. 2. However, the layers anodised in oxalic acid have smaller pore diameters and the hexagonal cells structure is only vaguely distinguished. As already mentioned, FEG-SEM images have been digitally analyzed to obtain the pore size distribution, Fig. 8(b). The average pore diameter calculated for this sample is 34 nm, which is only a slightly smaller value than those commonly reported in literature for this type of films (around 40 nm [12,30]). FEG-SEM images in cross section, Fig. 8(c), show that the pores are well aligned, parallel to each other.

Fig. 9 shows a STEM-HAADF image of an alumina membrane anodised in oxalic acid. Note again that the cell walls, one of which is marked with arrows appear slightly brighter than the pore walls. This situation is similar to that reported for the membranes prepared in phosphoric acid, Figs. 3 and 4, although the difference in intensity between both regions is smaller in this case.

The ultrathin TEM samples of these membranes obtained via anodising in oxalic acid are much more sensitive to damage by the electron beam than those prepared from the membranes obtained in phosphoric acid. This made impracticable X-EDS mapping on this sample. To overcome this difficulty, nanoanalytical work was carried out by means of Electron Energy Loss Spectroscopy (EELS). The use of this technique does allow much smaller exposure times, a much higher sensitivity to light elements and a much higher spatial resolution. The two latter factors are of major importance in a sample in which the electrolyte contaminant is a C-bearing anion (oxalate) and in which the dimensions of the pores and cell walls are much smaller.

Fig. 10(a) shows another STEM-HAADF image of a membrane anodised in oxalic acid. Fig. 10(b) plots the image intensity signal along the A-B line drawn on the STEM-HAADF image, which crosses one of the hexagonal cells passing through the centre of

Fig. 9. STEM-HAADF image of a porous anodic alumina membrane obtained in oxalic acid anodising. In some areas as the one marked with arrows the cell wall can be observed.

Fig. 10. (a) STEM-HAADF image of a porous alumina membrane anodised in oxalic acid. (b) STEM-HAADF signal intensity variation acquired simultaneously with the spectrum line (c) EELS 3D representation of a collection of 100 spectra acquired along the A-B line. (d) EELS spectra 1 and 2 extracted from the SI-EELS analysis.

the pore. Fig. 10(c) shows a collection of 100 EEL spectra recorded at consecutive points along this A-B line every 5 Å. The energy loss range represented in this spectrum-line experiment corresponds to that of the Al-L and C-K edges. Note how both signals do modify significantly along the electron beam path and how the C-K signal peaks up at the centre of the path where the Al-L peaks do almost disappear. There also seems to be a steep gradient of C-K concentration in this central part of the spectrum-line recording. If these spectra are correlated with the position of the beam, these results indicate that within the pore wall, the carbon signal reaches a maximum just at the pore edge and decreases very rapidly as the analysis moves along the pore wall towards the cell wall.

To illustrate this further, Fig. 10(d) depicts two EEL spectra extracted from the whole collection shown in Fig. 10(c), those corresponding positions marked as 1 and 2 on the STEM-HAADF image.

Spectrum number 1 was acquired in a 5 Å spot located close to the cell wall while number 2 was recorded in a spot just at the edge of the pore wall. Spectrum 1 contains the features of the Al-K edge but no C-K peaks can be detected. On the contrary, in position 2 the aluminium signal is very weak and the carbon signal is maximum.

To summarize the nanoanalytical study on the films prepared in oxalic acid, EELS spectrum-line experiments do clearly evidence the incorporation of C-bearing species to the film, very likely in the form of oxalate anions, into the pore wall area. The oxalate concentration peaks at locations very close to the pore edge and steeply decrease towards the cell wall, inside which only Al can be detected. These results agree with those obtained in [29] performing X-EDS analysis. However, membranes of 500 nm of thickness are studied in [29]. Then, the use of X-EDS in so thick samples limits the spatial resolution of the analysis to values which are very large in comparison with the usual dimensions of the wall thickness in this type of layers.

Since the atomic number of carbon is smaller than that of aluminium (Al = 13, C = 6), the average atomic number will decrease in the pore walls. This could explain the differences in the

HAADF-image intensity between the cell wall and the pore wall areas. Moreover, as it was also commented for the membranes anodised in phosphoric acid, the presence of ions from the electrolyte in the pore wall could change its structure and cause a density decrease, this also being another possible contribution to the STEM-HAADF image contrast.

Despite the weak differences in contrast of the STEM-HAADF images, the intensity profiles generated allow to measure the parameters of the hexagonal structure. As an example, Fig. 11 shows the image intensity variations along a line which crosses a cell wall, as shown in the STEM-HAADF image detail inset. The average cell wall thickness estimated from this image is 3.5 nm, whereas the thickness of the pore wall and the pore diameter are 17 and 50 nm, respectively. These figures lead to a D_{inner}/D_{outer} ratio close to 0.2, in good agreement with the values suggested by Gösele et al. for ordered membranes. However, it should be noticed

Fig. 11. Measurement of cell wall thickness in a porous alumina membrane anodised in oxalic acid employing the intensity profile obtained in the area showed in the STEM-HAADF image.

that the pore size measured from the STEM-HAADF intensity profiles is notably larger than that estimated from FEG-SEM images. These differences, in this particular case, in the pore size as determined from SEM and STEM-HAADF images may have different contributions: homogeneity of pore size distribution, lack of precise alignment during the cutting process which leads to sections which are not strictly normal to the pore axis, relaxation of the

Fig. 12. FEG-SEM images of a porous alumina membrane obtained in sulphuric acid anodising. (a) Top view. (b) Top view digitally analyzed to measure pore diameter (coloured regions) distribution. (c) Cross-section view showing the parallel growth of the nanopores. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

membranes after ultrathin sectioning and slight sample damage by the electron beam.

3.3. Sulphuric acid anodising

Fig. 12 shows FEG-SEM images of a membrane prepared in sulphuric acid. The low-mag view of the membrane in Fig. 12(a) looks like those obtained in oxalic acid but with smaller pore size. Digital analysis of high magnification images, like that in Fig. 12(b), as already done with previous samples allows estimating a pore diameter of about 32 nm. Likewise, the cross-section views, Fig. 12(c) show that the pores grew parallel, as expected.

Fig. 13 is one of the STEM-HAADF images obtained on alumina membranes prepared in sulphuric acid. Although the contrast is rather faint in this sample, it is still possible to distinguish the presence of the cell walls as a hexagonal net of brighter, very thin, lines. The much smaller dimensions of the pores, cell wall and pore wall complicates further the detailed analysis of these samples.

Measurements performed on a number of STEM-HAADF intensity profiles, as the one included in Fig. 14, indicate that the average values of cell wall thickness, pore wall thickness and pore diameter are in this case 3 nm, 16 nm and 23 nm, respectively. These values give a D_{inner}/D_{outer} ratio ≈ 0.18 , which fits exactly the $D_{inner}/D_{outer} \approx 0.2 \pm 0.02$ rule. The average pore diameter mea-

Fig. 13. STEM-HAADF image of a membrane prepared in sulphuric acid anodising. In some areas as the one marked with arrows the cell wall can be observed.

Fig. 14. Measurement of cell wall thickness in an alumina membrane prepared in sulphuric acid employing the intensity profile obtained in the area showed in the STEM-HAADF image.

Fig. 15. (a) STEM-HAADF image of a cell in a porous alumina membrane obtained in sulphuric acid. Compositional map of (b) Al and (c) S in the cell displayed in (a). Overlapped, intensity profile of X-EDS signal of Al (in b) and S (in c) along the line marked. (d) Intensity profiles of STEM-HAADF signal along the line marked in the image in (a).

sured with these intensity profiles (23 nm) is of the same order of magnitude of that estimated from FEG-SEM images (32 nm).

Concerning nanoanalytical studies on this sample, we have to mention first that the use of EEL Spectroscopy is not recommended in this case because of the overlap of the Al and S edges. So, although the ultrathin TEM samples of this type of anodic film are also quite sensitive to electron beam irradiation, STEM-X-EDS stands as the best choice to unveil the distribution of elements in these samples. Thus, we carried out STEM-X-EDS compositional mapping under recording conditions aiming at minimizing damage.

Fig. 15 shows a STEM-HAADF image of a cell, Fig. 15(a), and the compositional maps of Al and S in this cell, Fig. 15(b) and (c). It also includes (as insets) the intensity profiles of the X-EDS signals of Al and S along a line, marked on the compositional maps, which crosses a complete cell. The comparison of both maps suggests a parallel distribution of Al and S throughout the cell. Both signals present maxima at a position located about half the pore wall width. In fact the trend in the intensity profiles obtained from the elemental maps is the same as observed in the intensity profile of the STEM-HAADF signal, Fig. 15(d). Though the quality of the S map signal is not optimum, they do not present a minimum at the position of the cell wall. Direct spot analysis on the cell wall to confirm the presence of S inside this part of the film could not be performed because of severe sample damage. In any case the maps presented here suggest a roughly constant Al/S ratio throughout the pore wall, with no spatial shift between the maxima of the Al and S chemical signals, as it was previously described for the films prepared in phosphoric or oxalic acid. This qualitative aspect of the element distribution in the films prepared in sulphuric acid do clearly differ from those previously found for the P- and C-bearing species mentioned before.

4. Conclusions

Porous alumina layers anodised in ordered regimes in phosphoric, oxalic and sulphuric acid have been characterized morphologically and chemically at atomic scale. The morphological characterization was carried out by means of FEG-SEM and STEM-HAADF images. Digital analysis of these images have allowed us performing a statistically meaningful determination of several structural parameters of these films, as it is the case of pore size, pore wall thickness and cell wall thickness. Nanoanalytical characterization has been based on the use of STEM-EELS and STEM-X-EDS working either in spot, line or mapping modes.

The results obtained in the present work show that intensity profiles obtained from STEM-HAADF signal images can be fruitfully used to accurately estimate the dimensional features of the hexagonal cells in ordered anodic alumina membranes. The measurements carried out on the three types of films studied here follow the ratio rule proposed by Gösele et al., $D_{inner}/D_{outer} = 0.2 \pm 0.02$, where D_{inner} stands for the ion-contaminated pore wall thickness and D_{outer} for the ion-free cell wall thickness. Moreover, we have shown that STEM-HAADF imaging is the most suitable tool to properly evaluate the variations of density within these films, avoiding the contributions of variations in chemical composition or diffraction contrast effects which may interfere when bright field imaging techniques are used for this purpose. On the basis of these STEM-HAADF images we have revealed that in phosphoric acid anodising the density of the cell wall is higher than that of the pore wall.

Nanoanalytical studies have also confirmed the incorporation of anion species coming from the electrolyte solution into the film structure in all the analyzed cases. Moreover, these studies have allowed establishing detailed spatial distribution patterns for each of the electrolytes. We should highlight that our results do demon-

strate, for the first time, clear differences in the distribution of P-, C- and S-bearing species in this ordered films.

For the two firsts, the concentration of the anion shows a maximum within the pore wall. In the case of C this maximum occurs at positions adjacent to the pore, whereas it moves further inside the pore wall, roughly at the middle, in the case of the films anodized in phosphoric acid.

In contrast, the distribution of sulphur-containing species in the case of films anodized in sulphuric acid shows a somewhat uniform distribution throughout the pore wall, with no well-defined maxima.

In the case of the films prepared in phosphoric and oxalic acid, spot analyses have clearly shown the absence of anions within the cell wall region. In the case of the films prepared in sulphuric acid, both the much smaller dimensions of this structure and the high sensitivity to beam irradiation effects have precluded such an analysis, this being the only feature which could not be fixed in the present study.

The whole set of results presented here do also clearly point out the high potential of advanced transmission, scanning-transmission electron microscopy techniques in the characterization of these films. Moreover, the atomic-scale resolution element distribution patterns obtained with their use can be key information to probe currently available growth mechanisms models.

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